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Research Article

TO EVALUATE THE FREQUENCY OF DEPRESSION AMONG DIABETIC PATIENTS; A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

Dr. Sanaulhaq¹, Dr. Momina Shafique², Dr Riaz Ahmad³

¹RHQ hospital District Diamer Chilas, ²Azad Jammu and Kashmir Medical College
Muzaffarabad, ³Latin American school of Medicine (ELAM) Cuba.

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Abstract:

Objectives: The aim of our study was to evaluate the frequency among diabetic patients with depression.

Study design: A cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted at Medicine department, Saidu Teaching Hospital Swat for the duration of five months starting from March, 2020 to August, 2020.

Methodology: In the study informed consent was obtained after objectives of study were explained to the patients. With the help of one researcher a questionnaire (standard questionnaire by back) for each patient were complete. The Beck Depression Inventory, a 21-item screening questionnaire comprising 13 cognitive and 8 somatic questions was used to screen for depression. Depending on total score all the participants having depression were classified into four groups. In first group those patients were included having Minimal depression age range from 0 to 13 years, in second group those patients were included having Mild depression age range from 14 to 19 years, in third group those patients were included having Moderate depression age range from 20 to 28 years and the last group include those patients having Severe depression age range from 29 to 63 years.

Results: According to the study, results showed there were occurrence of mild depression among diabetic patients. Depression was not significantly associated with patients' age or gender. In the study there were 100 diabetic patients selected. In selected patients 34% were having age range from 20-40, 18% were having age range from 61- 80 and 48% were having age range from 41-60. According to gender, the sample ratio of male and female were 3:1. According to the stages of depression, 68% of patients had mild depression, 20% of patients had moderate depression and 12% of patients had minimal depression.

Conclusion: At the end of our study, we conclude that there was occurrence of depression among diabetic patients. Although the degree of depression was different, the average diabetic patient has a milder state of depression. It supposed that patients with diabetes should be screened regularly for depression and timely intervention if needed.

Keywords: Diabetes Clinic, Diabetes Type 1, Diabetes Type 2, Depression.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Sanaulhaq,

RHQ hospital District Diamer Chilas,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

According to an estimation by WHO the number of people affected by Diabetes by the year 2030 would be 350 million, with an average increase of 100% from year 2000 [1]. With the rise in Diabetes worldwide, the incidence among youngsters is skyrocketing, and so is its chronicity and complications [2,3]. Disability and higher mortality are just one side of the picture. The much darker side of Diabetes entails increased health care cost and decreased social productivity of the patient [4]. Diabetes is associated with depression and this depression is not only common among patients of diabetes but also in common population. However, the chances of having depression in diabetics are almost twice than that of in nondiabetics [5]. According to a research done in Karachi, Pakistan the incidence of depression among diabetics was significantly higher than general population [6]. Different studies show that there is strong link between preexisting depression and risk of developing diabetes [7,8]. Diabetes-depression package has a tremendous negative impact which entails physical and functional disability, financial burden both on individual and state and ultimately increased mortality [9,10].

Latest studies show that diabetic adults suffering from anxiety disorders are associated with less preferred glycemic studies [11,12]. In the clinical studies carried out, a methodical review established that increased anxiety symptoms were present in 40% of diabetic patients [13]. Among all the diabetics, about 14% showed generalized anxiety disorder which is one of the most common anxiety disorders [14] In the population-based studies that took place, the relation between diabetes and depression was reported to range from slight differences to twice the increase in risk [15,16]. The methods applied to these studies showed differences due to sample size, methods to identify depression and diabetes, sample characteristics and either a prospective or cross-sectional design was used. Another factor affecting the differences in studies can be chance variations in approximations of the strength of association. In the last five years a significant chunk of research related to diabetes-depression duo was done in west. Even though this condition is on the rise in Pakistan there is no significant and comprehensive research done in Pakistan, partly because our society neglects the

psychological aspects of life and partly due to less health education.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Medicine department, Saidu Teaching Hospital Swat for the duration of five months starting from March, 2020 to August, 2020. Non-probability convenient sampling technique were used. Definition of depression is that, a medical condition in which a person feels very sad, hopeless, and unimportant and often is unable to live in a normal way.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All diabetics within the age group of 20-80 and of either gender were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Diabetics from other medical facilities were excluded.
2. Patients with other predisposing factors for depression e.g., cancer were also excluded.

After clarifying the study objectives to patients, informed consent was obtained. A Performa questionnaire (the standard questionnaire by Beck) was completed for each patient with help from 1 investigator. The Beck Depression Inventory, a 21-item screening questionnaire comprising 13 cognitive and 8 somatic questions was used to screen for depression. After that, participants were classified into 4 groups of depression, namely; Minimal (0-13), Mild (14-19), Moderate (20-28) and Severe (29-63), depending on the total score. Independent and dependent variables were Diabetes Mellitus and Depression respectively. With depression as qualitative variable and no quantitative variable was there. We analyzed the data by using SPSS.21.0 For qualitative variables we calculated frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

This study is about depression among diabetic patients. The demographics are presented in Table 1, which shows that 34% of people were in age group 20-40, 48% in 41-60 and 18% in 61-80. Graph 1 show that the ration of male to female in sample was 3:1.

Table No 01: Age of Respondent

Age	Qty	%age
20-40 years	34	34%
41-60 years	48	48%
61-80 years	18	18%
Total	100	100%

As shown by table 2, the mean BDI score was 17.15 with a standard deviation of 3.48. This showed that there is presence of Mild Depression among the diabetes patients.

Table No 02: Beck Depression Inventory Total Score

Qty	Mean	Standard deviation	minimum	Maximum
100	17.15	3.482	4.0	27.0

Table 3 shows that the mean BDI score for those in age group 20-40 was 16.7 with a SD of 3.23, those in 41-60 was 17.0 with a SD of 3.4 and those in 61-80 was 18.33 with a SD of 4.04.

Table No 03: Beck Depression Inventory Total Score According to Age

Age	Qty	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
20-40	34	16.7353	3.23156	4.00	22.00
41-60	48	17.0000	3.40838	11.00	27.00
61-80	18	18.3333	4.04388	13.00	27.00
Total	100	17.1500	3.48264	4.00	27.00

Table 4 shows the mean score of BDI in males to be 17.1 with a SD of 3.36 while in females it was 17.24 with a SD of 3.88. The same results are presented in the form of graph in graph 2. Graph 3 shows the mean and SD in a graphical form, where mean BDI score is 17.15 with SD of 3.48

Table No 04: Beck Depression Inventory Total Score According to Gender

Gender	Qty	Mean	S. D	Minimum	Maximum
Male	75	17.1200	3.36902	4.00	27.00
Female	25	17.2400	3.87599	12.00	27.00
Total	100	17.1500	3.48264	4.00	27.00

Table 5 shows that 12% of people have minimal depression, 68% have mild depression and 20% have moderate depression. Graph 4 represents the same results in graphical form.

Table No 06: Stages of Depression According to Gender

Stage of depression	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Minimal Depression	Qty	8	4
	%age	10.7%	16.0%
Mild Depression	Qty	52	16
	%age	69.3%	64.0%
Moderate Depression	Qty	15	5
	%age	20.0%	20.0%
Total	Qty	75	25
	%age	100.0%	100.0%

Stages of Depression

Table No 07: Stages of depression According to Age

Stage of depression		Age group			Total
		20-40	41-60	61-80	
Minimal Depression	Qty	4	7	1	12
	%age	11.8%	14.6%	5.6%	12.0%
Mild Depression	Qty	26	32	10	68
	%age	76.5%	66.7%	55.6%	68.0%
Moderate Depression	Qty	4	9	7	20
	%age	11.8%	18.8%	38.9%	20.0%
Total	Qty	34	48	18	100
	%age	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %

■ Minimal ■ Mild ■ Moderate

DISCUSSION:

This study "Prevalence of Depression in Diabetics attending Diabetic Clinic, Jinnah Hospital." was conducted to find out frequency of Depression in Diabetics attending Diabetic Clinic, Jinnah Hospital. Evidence from prospective and cross-sectional studies demonstrates that the presence of diabetes doubles the risk of co morbid depression. This commonly overlooked co morbidity affects more than one quarter of the diabetic population, making its recognition and treatment in diabetic patients clinically relevant. According to a research done about Prevalence of Co morbid Depression in Adults with Diabetes by Ryan J Anderson and his team, [5/17] the odds of depression in diabetics was twice as those in non-diabetics. This

is in accordance with the findings of our research where we found a prevalence of mean state of mild depression among diabetics. According to a research done in Karachi about association of depression in type 2 diabetics, [6] there was a significant association with an odds ratio of mild depression to be 3.86 and moderate to severe level to be 3.41.

Another research on association of depression in type 2 diabetes by Wayne J Kenton and his team, [12] showed that there were a 2.3-fold increase in deaths of patient with major depression as compared to no or mild depression. This is in accordance with our results where the diabetes was associated with a prevalence of mild depression. Our research findings indicated that

there was a no significant gender association with depression among diabetics. However, a research done on prevalence of anxiety in adults with diabetes [18] showed that depression and anxiety was 55.3% more common in females as compared to men.

CONCLUSION:

From this study we concluded that there is a prevalence of depression among diabetics. Though the depression was of varying degree, on average there is a mild state of depression among diabetics. Early diagnosis of depression may improve the quality of life of patients.

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